
Growth, Vibrational and Antimicrobial Activity Studies on Glycinium Dihydrogen Phosphate Complex Crystal

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Abstract The single crystal of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate was grown at room temperature by the slow evaporation method. The well grown transparent crystal was subjected to the single crystal XRD study for confirmation. The powder XRD study shows crystalline nature and purity of the title crystal. The vibrational analysis of title crystal was accomplished through the FT-IR and FT-Raman spectroscopy techniques. The optical property and energy gap was analyzed by the UV-Visible spectroscopy study. The surface morphology and elemental analysis were done with the help of SEM with EDX analyzes. The antimicrobial activity of title crystal was tested against the four different micro-organisms by disc diffusion method.

Keyword: glycinium dihydrogen phosphate, XRD, antimicrobial activity, FT-IR, FT-Raman, SEM, EDX.

1. Introduction

Glycine is the simplest and sweet-tasting non-essential amino acid which is necessary ones for a healthy digestive system [1]. It is found in various high-protein foods like beans, fish, meat, milk, and cheese [2]. It is known as an anti-aging amino acid which is used to prevent the cellular damage and various signs of aging [3]. According to some researches on glycine showed that it can also inhibit some types of cancer through antioxidants [4, 5]. It has three different polymorphismsie., α -glycine, β -glycine and γ -glycine [6-8]. Many researchers to grow glycine single crystal with different combination of inorganic salts such as phosphoric acid [9], hydrofluoric acid [10], hydro bromic acid [11], nitric acid [12] and hydro chloric acid [13]. Also, the structural studies of amino acid complexes were reported by many authors in the past few years [14, 15]. Glycine is known to react with the ortho phosphoric acid leading to the formation of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate and the crystal structure was already reported by Averbuch-Pouchot et al. [16]. In the present work, single crystal XRD and powder XRD, FT-IR, FT-Raman, UV-Visible spectroscopy, SEM with EDAX studies were carried out. Apart from these, the antibacterial activity study seems to be enhanced because none of them were reported to this property for this compound.

2. Materials and Method

Materials

Commercially available raw materials of analar grade of glycine and ortho phosphoric acid were purchased from the local scientific company, Madurai, India.

Slow evaporation Method

The equimolar ratio (2: 1) of glycine and ortho phosphoric acid were dissolved in distilled water and it was stirred for 1 hour. Then it was filtered using high quality filter paper. The filtered solution was poured into the petri dish.

Now the petri dish was tightly closed with thick filter paper due to minimize rate of evaporation at room temperature. After a period of 10 days bulk transparent crystals of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate were harvested. The photographic view of grown crystal is depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1: Grown crystal of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate

3. Characterization Techniques

A good quality grown crystal of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis using Bruker SMART APEX CCD diffractometer with Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). The XPERT-PRO X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.54060 \text{ \AA}$) radiation was used to record the powder diffraction pattern. The FT-IR vibrational spectrum was recorded by using SHIMADZU FT-IR spectrometer in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} . Also, the FT-Raman spectrum was recorded by using the BRUKER: RFS 27 Raman spectrometer in the wavenumber range 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The optical absorption spectrum has been recorded with SHIMADZU-UV1800 double beam spectrometer in the wavelength range 200-1100 nm in steps of 1 nm. The surface morphology and elemental analysis has been carried out by CARLZEISS EVO18 scanning electron microscope. The antimicrobial activity of parent and its complex crystals were tested against four different kinds of micro-organisms by disc diffusion method.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Single crystal XRD

The unit cell parameter of the title compound was determined using the Bruker SMART APEX CCD single crystal X-ray diffractometer. This result showed that cell parameter values of the grown crystal are exactly matched with already reported values [16]. The experimentally obtained cell parameter values of title crystal are tabulated in Table 1.

Figure 2: Molecular structure of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

The single crystal XRD study reveals that the grown crystal is a complex one, since the one proton of phosphoric acid is liberated and protonated with glycine NH_2 group, leading to formation of glyciniumcation and dihydrogen phosphate anion. Here, the carboxylic group of glycine is not deprotonated and so its configuration became as

HOOC-CH₂-NH₃⁺. Also this study confirms the grown crystal crystallizes in the monoclinic system with space group P2₁/c. The molecular structure of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal is shown in figure 2.

Table 1: Crystallographic data of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

Lattice Parameters	Present Study	Already reported [16]
Compound name	Glycinium dihydrogen phosphate	Glycinium dihydrogen phosphate
Empirical formula	C ₂ H ₆ NO ₂ ⁺ H ₂ PO ₄ ⁻	C ₂ H ₆ NO ₂ ⁺ H ₂ PO ₄ ⁻
Molecular formula weight	173.06	173.06
Unit cell Dimensions	a = 9.575 (3) (Å) b = 7.838(3) (Å) c = 9.248 (5) (Å) α = 90° β = 114.5 (4)° γ = 90°	a = 9.580 (2) (Å) b = 7.840 (2) (Å) c = 9.249 (3) (Å) α = 90° β = 114.7 (2)° γ = 90°
Volume	625 (Å) ³	631 (Å) ³
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c	P2 ₁ /c

4.2. Powder XRD Analysis

The powder XRD pattern of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal is shown in figure 3. The appearance of sharp and strong peaks confirmed the good crystallinity and purity of the grown crystal. The characteristic peak of this compound has seemed at around 29.80°. The INDX software was used to index the PXRD patterns. The average crystalline size of title crystal was determined by using the Debye-Scherrer equation, which can be written as,

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta}$$

where,

D = average crystallite size

K = dimensionless shape factor (0.94)

λ = wavelength of X-ray radiation (Cu Kα = 1.54060 Å)

θ = diffraction angle

β = Full width at half maximum intensity

The Dislocation density can be calculated from,

$$\delta = \frac{1}{D^2} \text{ m}^2$$

where,

δ is dislocation density,

D is the crystallite size

Figure 3: Diffraction patterns for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

For glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal, the average crystalline size was found to be as 27 nm. Also, the dislocation density was determined as $1.37 \times 10^{15} \text{m}^{-2}$.

4.3. Vibrational analysis

The glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal has $[\text{NH}_3]^+$, CH_2 , COOH and $[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]$ functional groups. The FT-IR and FT-Raman spectra of title compound are shown in figure 4 and figure 5 respectively. The detailed wavenumber assignments for the glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal are presented in Table 2.

Vibrations of $-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ cation

Normally the antisymmetric and symmetric stretching modes of $-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ group were found in the region of 3200 cm^{-1} and 2800 cm^{-1} [17]. In the present study, $\nu_{\text{as}}-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ mode is identified as a strong broad band at 3171 cm^{-1} in IR and as a weak band at 3140 cm^{-1} in Raman spectra for this mode. Also $\nu_{\text{s}}-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ mode is attributed at 2965 cm^{-1} , 2889 cm^{-1} , 2825 cm^{-1} in IR and at 2970 cm^{-1} , 2887 cm^{-1} , 2821 cm^{-1} in Raman spectra. The antisymmetric and symmetric bending wavenumbers for $-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ group were normally expected to fall in the region of $1625\text{-}1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1550\text{-}1505 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively [17, 18]. For the title crystal, $\delta_{\text{as}}-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ mode is assigned at 1611 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum and the $\delta_{\text{s}}-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ band is attributed at 1554 cm^{-1} , 1506 cm^{-1} in IR and at 1568 cm^{-1} , 1511 cm^{-1} in Raman spectra. The experimentally observed stretching and bending modes of $-\text{[NH}_3\text{]}^+$ group for the title compound are deviated from the free ion due to the presence of hydrogen bonding network.

Figure 4: FT-IR spectrum of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

Figure 5: FT-Raman spectrum of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

Table 2: Wavenumber assignments for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal in FT – IR and FT – Raman spectra

FT – IR ($\bar{\nu}$ / cm^{-1})	FT– Raman ($\bar{\nu}$ / cm^{-1})	Assignment
3171 (s, br)	3140 (w)	$\nu_{\text{as}}[\text{NH}_3]^+$
3000 (sh)	3006 (m)	ν (O-H)
2965 (w)	2970(s)	$\nu_{\text{s}}[\text{NH}_3]^+$; $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CH}_2)$
2889 (w)	2887(m)	$\nu_{\text{s}}[\text{NH}_3]^+$; $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{CH}_2)$
2825 (w)	2821 (m)	$\nu_{\text{s}}[\text{NH}_3]^+$
1794 (w)	-	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C=O})$
1734(m)	-	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C=O})$
1645(w)	1667 (w)	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{C=O})$
1611(m)	-	$\delta_{\text{as}}[\text{NH}_3]^+$
1554(sh)	1568(m)	$\delta_{\text{s}}[\text{NH}_3]^+$
1506(m)	1511(w)	$\delta_{\text{s}}[\text{NH}_3]^+$
1451 (w)	1447(m)	$\rho(\text{CH}_2)$; $\beta(\text{O-H})$
1412(m)	1408(m)	$\beta(\text{O-H})$
1333(s)	1322(s)	$\omega(\text{CH}_2)$
1239(w)	1244 (w)	$\nu(\text{C-O})$; $t(\text{CH}_2)$; $\beta(\text{P-OH})$
1191(sh)	-	$\nu(\text{P=O})$
1134 (sh)	1138 (w)	$\nu(\text{C-N})$; $\nu_{\text{as}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$
1109 (m)	1109 (w)	$\nu(\text{C-N})$; $\nu(\text{C-C})$
1064(sh)	-	$\nu_{\text{as}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$
1030(m)	1034 (w)	$\nu(\text{C-N})$; $\nu(\text{C-C})$
976(sh)	-	$\nu_{\text{as}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$
891(s)	891(m)	$\gamma(\text{O-H})$; $\nu_{\text{s}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$; $\nu(\text{P-OH})$
839(sh)	861(w)	$\gamma(\text{P-OH})$; $\nu(\text{C-C})$
606 (w)	-	$\delta_{\text{as}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$
501(w)	-	$\delta_{\text{as}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$
417 (sh)	-	$\delta_{\text{as}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$
-	359(w)	$\delta_{\text{s}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$
-	342(w)	$\delta_{\text{s}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$

w–weak; s– strong; m– medium; sh- shoulder; ν – stretching; ν_{s} – symmetric stretching; ν_{as} –anti symmetric stretching; δ_{s} - symmetric bending; δ_{as} - antisymmetric bending; γ – out-of-plane bending; β – in-plane bending; ρ - rocking; t-twisting; ω -wagging

Vibrations of $[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$ anion

In the free state, the phosphate ion exist in T_d symmetry which has symmetric stretching $\nu_1(A_1)$, antisymmetric stretching $\nu_3(F_2)$, symmetric bending $\nu_2(E)$ and antisymmetric bending $\nu_4(F_2)$ internal vibrational modes. These wavenumbers occur at 936 cm^{-1} (ν_{sym}), 420 cm^{-1} (δ_{sym}), 1004 cm^{-1} (ν_{asym}) and 573 cm^{-1} (δ_{asym}) [19, 20]. But, the molecular symmetry of $[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$ ion reduces to C_{2v} symmetry owing to the presence of two P–OH bonds. As a result, ν_2 splits into two components ($A_1 + A_2$) and ν_3 and ν_4 split into three components ($A_1 + B_1 + B_2$) each [19]. The symmetric stretching mode (A_1) normally occurs at 880 cm^{-1} and the symmetric bending mode E splits into two, appearing at 385 (A_1) and 373 (A_2) cm^{-1} . The antisymmetric stretching mode (F_2) splits into three occurring at 1090 (A_1), 1123 (B_1) and 940 (B_2) cm^{-1} . The antisymmetric bending mode (F_2) has also lost its degeneracy and was expected to occur at 525 (A_1), 510 (B_1) and 503 (B_2) cm^{-1} . All the species were both infrared and Raman active except for A_2 species, which was only Raman active [21]. In the present study, $\nu_{\text{as}}[\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4]^-$ mode is identified at 1064 (A_1), 1134 (B_1), 976 (B_2) cm^{-1} in IR and the symmetric stretching mode is observed in IR and

Raman spectra at 891(A₁), 891(A₁) cm⁻¹ respectively. Also, the symmetric bending mode of this group is attributed at 359, 342 cm⁻¹ in Raman spectrum only and antisymmetric bending mode is identified at 606(A₁), 417(B₁) and 501 (B₂) cm⁻¹ in IR spectrum only. All these assignments confirm the existence of dihydrogen phosphate anion in the C_{2v} symmetry and it is clearly identified from the Table 3. The P–OH group has a strong band in the region 1040 – 810 cm⁻¹ which is due to the stretching of P–OH bands [21]. The medium bands occur at 891cm⁻¹ in IR and at 891 cm⁻¹ in Raman spectra are assigned to P–OH stretching vibration of title crystal. The in-plane and out-of-plane bending vibrations of P–OH group occur in the region 1350–1200 cm⁻¹ and 950–750 cm⁻¹ respectively [22].

Table 3: Vibrational distribution of [PO₄]³⁻ ion to [H₂PO₄]⁻ ion

T _d [PO ₄] ³⁻ (cm ⁻¹)	C _{2v} [H ₂ PO ₄] ⁻ (cm ⁻¹)	Present Study (cm ⁻¹)
A ₁ (936)	A ₁ (887)	A ₁ (891)
E (420)	A ₁ (357)	A ₁ (359)
	A ₂ (338)	A ₂ (342)
F ₂ (1004)	A ₁ (1096)	A ₁ (1064)
	B ₁ (1132)	B ₁ (1134)
	B ₂ (964)	B ₂ (976)
F ₂ (573)	A ₁ (529)	A ₁ (606)
	B ₁ (453)	B ₁ (417)
	B ₂ (500)	B ₂ (501)

For the title compound these modes are identified in IR spectrum at 1239 cm⁻¹, 839 cm⁻¹ and in Raman spectrum at 1244 cm⁻¹, 861 cm⁻¹ respectively. The stretching vibrations of P=O generally give rise to strong band in the region 1300 – 1140 cm⁻¹ for dihydrogen phosphate. The absorption bands at 1191 cm⁻¹ in IR spectrum is assigned to P=O stretching mode of glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal.

CH₂ group vibrations

The regions between 3000–2900 cm⁻¹ and 2900 and 2800 cm⁻¹ were identified as antisymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of CH₂ group respectively [23- 25]. The CH₂ symmetric stretching vibration for 6'-(3-Bromo phenyl)-7'-nitro-1',6',7',7a'-tetrahydro-3'H-spiro[indeno[1,2-b]quinoxaline-11,5'-pyrrolo[1,2-c]thiazole] molecule at 2929 cm⁻¹ in IR and at 2942 cm⁻¹ in Raman spectra for antisymmetric stretching mode of CH₂ group were reported by Muthuselvi et al. [26]. Also, the symmetric stretching mode of the CH₂ group was assigned at 2871, 2867 cm⁻¹ in both spectra. In the present work, bands are recognized at 2965 cm⁻¹, 2889 cm⁻¹ and at 2970 cm⁻¹, 2887 cm⁻¹ in both spectra is assigned to ν_{as}(CH₂) and ν_s(CH₂) modes respectively. The CH₂ bending mode wavenumber assignment orders were specified as follows: CH₂scis > CH₂wag > CH₂ twist > CH₂ rock [27]. The CH₂ scissoring, wagging and twisting modes fall in the range 1482–1437 cm⁻¹, 1390–1180 cm⁻¹ and 730 cm⁻¹- 720 cm⁻¹ respectively [26, 27]. In the present study, the absorption bands at 1451 cm⁻¹ in IR and at 1447 cm⁻¹ in Raman spectra is assigned to CH₂ scissoring mode. Also, CH₂ wagging and twisting modes are attributed at the 1333 cm⁻¹, 1239 cm⁻¹ (IR), 1322 cm⁻¹ (Raman). The rocking mode is not identified for title compound. The CH₂ group vibrational wavenumbers is not much shifting which reveals that this group does not make any bonding with other groups.

Vibrations of COOH group

The carboxylic group C=O antisymmetric and symmetric stretching wavenumbers occur in the region of 1720-1680 cm⁻¹ and 1680-1640 cm⁻¹ respectively [28]. In the present study, the bands arise at 1794, 1734 cm⁻¹ in IR is assigned to ν_{as} (C=O) mode and the bands are identified at 1645 cm⁻¹ in IR and 1667 cm⁻¹ in Raman is assigned to the ν_s(C=O) mode. The ν (C-O) mode normally occurs in the region of 1320–1210 cm⁻¹ [29]. The wavenumber at 1239 cm⁻¹ in IR spectrum is attributed to ν (C-O) mode. The O–H stretch from CO–OH group was identified at 3065–2826 cm⁻¹[26]. It is ascribed as a weak bands at 3000 cm⁻¹ and at 3006 cm⁻¹ in both spectra for title compound. The in-plane and out-of plane bending wavenumbers of O–H group appears in the region between 1440–1395 cm⁻¹ and 960–875 cm⁻¹ respectively [28, 29]. In the present work, β(O–H) mode is observed at 1451 cm⁻¹, 1412 cm⁻¹ in IR and

at 1447 cm^{-1} , 1408 cm^{-1} in Raman spectra respectively. Also $\gamma(\text{O-H})$ mode is attributed at 891 cm^{-1} in both spectra of title compound.

Vibrations of other groups

The stretching and bending modes C-C group normally falls in the range $1117\text{--}870\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [30]. The C-N absorption bands for aliphatic amines appear in the region of $1250\text{--}1020\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [30]. In the present study the bands identified at 1109 cm^{-1} , 1030 cm^{-1} , 839 cm^{-1} in IR spectrum and at 1104 cm^{-1} , 1034 cm^{-1} , 861 cm^{-1} in Raman spectrum is assigned to the $\nu(\text{C-C})$ mode of title compound. Also, the $\nu(\text{C-N})$ mode is attributed at 1134 cm^{-1} and 1138 cm^{-1} in both spectra. The other bands assigned to this mode mixed with C-C stretching vibration.

4.4. Optical analysis

The SHIMADZU-UV1800 double beam spectrometer was used to obtain the absorbance spectrum of title crystal in the wavelength range $200\text{--}1100\text{ nm}$. The experimentally recorded absorbance spectrum is shown in Figure 6. The lower cut-off wavelength was found to be at 240 nm . The title crystal has 100% transmittance in the entire visible region which makes usefulness of this material in optical application. The Tauc's relation $(\alpha h\nu)^2 = A(h\nu - E_g)$ was used to determine energy gap E_g by plotting the $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ Vs photon energy and extrapolate the linear portion of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ to the photon energy axis gives the energy gap value of title crystal

Figure 6: Absorbance spectrum for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

Figure 7: Optical band gap for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

The energy band gap was found at 5.38 eV from the Figure 7 and this band gap value reveals that the grown crystal is a typical of dielectric material.

4.5. SEM with EDX Analyzes

The SEM with EDX analyzes was used to analyze morphology and elemental composition of the title crystal. The SEM micro photographic images of title crystal with two different magnifications are illustrated in Figure.8. The glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal has smooth surface and well defined hexagonal shape morphology. These images revealed that the grown crystal has small voids and porous nature in the surface. However, the major part of the crystal has well defined hexagonal shape.

Figure 8: SEM photograph for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

The EDX spectrum for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal is displayed in Figure.9. The elemental composition present in crystal is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Elemental composition for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

Elements	Glycinium dihydrogen phosphate	
	Atomic%	Weight %
C	59.42	51.74
O	39.09	45.34

Figure 9: EDX chart for glycinium dihydrogen phosphate crystal

From the EDX spectrum, the presence of C and O elements are confirmed in the glyciniuim dihydrogen phosphate crystal.

4.6. Antimicrobial activity study

The *Bacillus subtilis*, *Micrococcus*, *Salmonella typhi* and *Pseudomonas* micro-organisms were tested to analyze the antimicrobial activity of glycine and glyciniuim dihydrogen phosphate crystals by disc diffusion method. The photographic view of bacterial screening for parent and its complex crystals with 50 µg/ml and 100 µg /l concentrations are shown in figure.10a and 10b respectively. The measured diameter zone of inhibition of these microorganisms is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Effective values of inhibited zone for glycine and glyciniuim dihydrogen phosphate crystal

S. No.	Micro-organisms	Zone of inhibition for glycine		Zone of inhibition for glyciniuim dihydrogen phosphate crystal	
		50 µl (mm)	100 µl (mm)	50 µl (mm)	100 µl (mm)
1.	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL
2.	<i>Micrococcus</i>	NIL	4	NIL	NIL
3.	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL
4.	<i>Pseudomonas</i>	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL

*NIL- No antimicrobial activity; mm- Zone of inhibition

Figure 10a: Photographic view showing inhibition region of four different micro-organisms at 50 µg/ml and 100 µg/l concentrations against glycine crystal

Figure 10b: Photographic view showing inhibition region of four different micro-organisms at 50 µg/ml and 100 µg/l concentrations against glyciniuim dihydrogen complex crystal

From the Table 4, it is clear that glycine and its complex crystals have no antimicrobial activity against four different test bacteria. But, the glycine crystal shows the effective zone of inhibition (4 mm) for Micrococcus organism in 100 µl concentration.

5. Conclusion

The slow evaporation technique was used to grow the glycinium dihydrogen phosphate complex crystal successfully at room temperature. It has monoclinic crystal system with the space group $P2_1/c$ which was confirmed by single-crystal XRD technique. The average crystalline size of grown crystal was found to be as 27 nm from the PXRD patterns and the peaks were indexed using the INDX software. Further, the presence of various functional groups and elements were verified using FT-IR and FT-Raman spectroscopy and Energy dispersive X-ray studies. The SEM analyzes shows that the title crystal has smooth surface and well defined hexagonal shape. Also, the optical band gap was determined as 5.38 eV by UV- Visible spectroscopy technique. The grown parent and its complex crystals were involved in an antibacterial activity against certain four micro-organisms by disc diffusion method. This study revealed that the pure glycine and glycinium dihydrogen complex crystals have no bacterial screening effect.

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